

The political consequences of mobilizing voters in hybrid regimes: Experimental evidence from Zimbabwe

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1: Introduction

This document describes the pre-analysis plan for an evaluation of a peer voter mobilization program carried out by a consortium of 11 Zimbabwean civil society organizations funded and coordinated by the Harare office of the National Democratic Institute (NDI). The program will be carried out during a six-month period in 2022.

In this project, we examine the impact of a peer voter mobilization program on the implementing activists, i.e., “champions.” More specifically, we will ask: (i) whether champions who participated in the program are more likely to engage in different forms of political activity than non-participants, (ii) whether the effect of peer voter mobilization programs on the mobilizers is contingent on the type of peer that they tried to mobilize, and (iii) what mechanisms link the relationship between mobilizing peers and various political outcomes.

This research project will be conducted in parallel with Dendere and Young’s (2022) “Peer-to-peer voter mobilization in a hybrid regime: Experimental evidence from Zimbabwe.” Dendere and Young (2022) examine the effect of NDI’s peer voter mobilization project on the voters who are being mobilized. This project, in contrast, focuses on the effect of NDI’s voter mobilization project on the mobilizers.

2: Motivation and Theory

2.1: Motivation

First, most research on voter mobilization campaigns has focused on its impact on voters. There is much less research, however, about the impact of voter mobilization campaigns on the implementing activists (Kalla and Broockman 2022). Second, the literature has largely focused on voter mobilization campaigns in the United States. We know far less, however, about the effect of these programs in hybrid regimes like Zimbabwe. Thus, we aim to understand how voter mobilization campaigns in hybrid regimes may shape the political behavior and attitudes of the implementing activists.

2.2: Theory

Participating in a voter mobilization campaign should promote greater political participation and downstream cooperation with outgroup individuals among the mobilizers. In terms of political participation, the experience of mobilizing voters should increase the likelihood that they will participate in collective action. This is based on the finding that political participation promotes further political participation because it enables “the imagining of different futures and the positive judgment that change was possible as the result of one’s own action” (Wood 2003: 240). Thus, we posit that mobilizing voters for elections may lead the mobilizers to engage in other forms of political participation.

In terms of downstream cooperation with outgroup individuals, mobilizing others to vote will promote political cooperation with individuals who may belong to a different social or political group. Kalla and Broockman (2022) found, for example, that voter mobilization campaigns reduced affective polarization among the mobilizers. In other words, the personal-persuasion campaigns led the mobilizers to engage in perspective-getting, that is, hearing narratives from—and about—the outgroup individuals that they otherwise would have never heard. Thus, participating in these campaigns may decrease the social distance, and political animus felt toward outgroup individuals. This, in turn, may enable greater cooperation.

Conversely, it is possible that participating in voter mobilization campaigns may impede downstream political cooperation and the level of outgroup cooperation if mobilizers have bad experiences. First, failure to convince peers to register and turn out to vote may lead the mobilizer to have a more negative perception of their internal political efficacy—their capacity to understand and shape political outcomes. Similarly, the perceived failure of the voter mobilization project to make an impact on electoral outcomes may lead to a perceived decrease in external political efficacy—the extent to which the state is responsive to civilian demands (Niemi, Craig, and Mattei 2014). For example, mobilizers might believe that there is a lower level of external political efficacy if the election results are thought to have been rigged and, therefore, illegitimate. Widespread belief in the illegitimacy of election results is more likely to be a significant issue in hybrid regimes like Zimbabwe. Thus, a decrease in internal and/or external political efficacy may cause the mobilizers to believe that political participation of all kinds—electoral or non-electoral and online or offline—are futile. Lower levels of collective action may occur as a result.

Participating in voter mobilization campaigns may also decrease rather than increase outgroup cooperation. The claim that personal-persuasion campaigns will increase social distance and affective polarization presupposes the validity of the contact hypothesis i.e., intergroup contact can reduce prejudice (Pettigrew 1998) It is also possible, however, that intergroup contact can promote negative perceptions of the outgroup by making intergroup differences more salient (Paolini, Harwood, and Rubin 2010). Similarly, failure to mobilize outgroup individuals may lead the mobilizers to have more negative views of outgroup individuals. This, in turn, may lead to less outgroup cooperation.

We expect that participation in the champions program will have two immediate effects on the champions: it will increase the amount of time and effort that they put into getting their friends and family registered to vote, and it will increase their knowledge of the voter registration process. We consider these outcomes to be manipulation checks as they are things that the program is designed to directly affect.

Figure 1 presents our theoretical framework as a diagram.

Figure 1: Causal diagram of champions program

3: Inquiry

What is the impact of mobilizing peers to vote on mobilizers in a hybrid regime? More specifically, we ask if participating in a voter mobilization program will lead to (i) greater political participation and (ii) greater cooperation with outgroup individuals. This is our primary research question. To answer this question, we will estimate the intent-to-treat (ITT) effect of a champion being assigned to participate in the voter mobilization program or not.

Second, we are interested in understanding a number of conditional ITTs that will help us understand how the program works and how it might be scaled up to have the biggest impact. Will peer mobilization lead to greater political participation among mobilizers when mobilizers have stronger preexisting social ties to the peers? Will peer mobilization lead to greater political participation among mobilizers when mobilizers and peers are more demographically similar? Will peer mobilization promote greater outgroup cooperation among mobilizers when they mobilize outgroup (non-copartisan) peers?

Last, we are interested in the mechanisms that link peer mobilization to the political behavior of mobilizers. We ask if the electoral and non-electoral political behavior of champions is impacted by (i) the champions' sense of civic duty, (ii) the champions' perceived social incentives (ingroup),

(iii) the champions' external political efficacy, (iv) the champions' internal political efficacy, and (v) the champions' perceptions of the (partisan) outgroup.

We will estimate the ITTs by comparing the outcome measures of champions assigned to the peer mobilization treatment and those champions assigned to the control group. While we will measure compliance in terms of whether champions actually attempt to mobilize the peers they are asked to target and will estimate the ITT of the treatment condition on compliance. However, we will not explicitly target the complier average causal effect. Instead, we will treat compliance as a potential mechanism that might help explain variation in our estimated ITTs. Our estimands are population average causal effects, where the population is the pool of recruited potential champions and eligible peers. Our strategy for estimating each of these quantities of interest is described in more detail in Section 5.

4: Data

4.1: Experimental Sample, 4.2: Interventions, 4.3: Randomization

4.4: Sampling

Some of our measurement strategies will require us to sample a subset of the 1600 potential champions, 4800+ P1s, and 2400 P2s¹ because we do not have the resources to measure outcomes for everyone. Our main outcomes of interest such as electoral and non-electoral political participation are at the level of the champions.

4.4.1 Champions sample

We will conduct an endline survey with all the 1,600 champions. The sample will be divided into the champions who participated in the voter mobilization project—the treated pool—and the champions who have not participated in the mobilization project—the control pool.

4.4.2 Qualitative Sample

We will select an additional set of CSO staff, potential champions, and peers from four of the CSOs for more in-depth qualitative interviews. We will use these qualitative interviews to 1) better understand the potential mechanisms, and 2) develop a set of more practical suggestions for strengthening the program if it is scaled up. This sample will be designed to maximize diversity across region, type of constituent, and champions program size.

4.5 Measurement

4.5.1 Measurement Strategies

We will measure outcomes with the potential champions, who are already familiar with the program and have personally volunteered to participate, via automated WhatsApp message surveys following the methodology developed by the Stanford Immigration Policy Lab using Twilio. We will

¹ We will identify the P2s in the baseline survey of P1s. We plan to survey 1600 P1s. Assuming that half of them accept to register three P2s we would have a pool of 2400 P2s.

attempt to survey all the potential champions via WhatsApp chat. We will follow up with a subset of champions who do not respond to the automated chat messages with enumerator-administered phone calls.

We have several strategies for collecting data in addition to the surveys. First, we have registration data that includes a set of basic demographic characteristics on all potential champions and peers (age group, gender, constituency). Second, we will match champions and peers by constituency to administrative data on election results from the previous election and proxies for the cost of voter registration like whether there was a mobile voter registration event in that constituency during the champions program and distance to the nearest voting center. Third, we will spend approximately four weeks observing the program implementation and interviewing the CSO staff and participants with four of the CSOs. Finally, we will collect administrative data from the CSOs on the program, including attendance records, the curriculum, and details of additional contacts with the trained and untrained potential champions.

4.5.2 Outcomes of Interest

This section describes the outcomes that we expect might be changed by the treatment as primary outcomes of interest, mechanisms, manipulation checks, secondary outcomes, and unintended consequences.

Primary Outcome 1: Downstream Political Participation. Our first key outcome of interest is the downstream political participation of champions. We will ask all participants the following questions:

“In the last three months, have you:

- 1) Posted anything on social media like Facebook or WhatsApp about voter registration?
- 2) Gotten together with others to raise an issue?
- 3) Have you attended a community meeting?

2- Yes, once; 3- Yes, several times; 4-Yes, often; 0-No; -99-Don't know

4) When you get together with your friends or family, would you say you discuss how well your MP or councilor is doing for the community:

1- Frequently; 2-Occasionally; 3-Never; 4- Don't know/Refuse

5) Do you plan to vote in the 2023 election?

4-Yes, definitely; 3- Yes, probably; 2-No, probably not; 1-No, definitely not; -99=Don't know/Refuse

6) In the last three months, how often would you say that you got news about current events?

4- Everyday; 3- A few times per week; 2- A few times per month; 1- Less than once per month

7) In the last three months, have you asked anyone for information about public services in your area, like water or electricity?

3- Yes; 2- No; 1- Not sure

The question about social media activity will measure the effect of mobilizing peers on *Online Political Participation*, while the questions about “getting together with others” will measure the effect of mobilizing peers on *Nonpartisan Political Participation*. The questions on campaign rallies and working for a candidate are measuring *Partisan Political Participation*. We will combine all five into a single index of downstream political participation by taking the average of these three sub-indices. ***Champion*** ***endline survey***.

Primary Outcome 2: Downstream Cooperation with Outgroup Individuals. Our second key outcome of interest is the downstream cooperation of champions with outgroup individuals. We will ask all participants the two following questions:

“In the last three months, have you:

- 1) Talked about the election with someone with different values or beliefs than you?
- 2) Joined a money club or done business with someone with values or beliefs than you?

2- Yes, once; 3- Yes, several times; 4-Yes, often; 0-No; -99-Don’t know

The question about election conversations will measure the effect of mobilizing peers on *Political Cooperation with Outgroup Individuals*, while the question about volunteering will measure *Civic Cooperation with Outgroup Individuals*. Our main analysis will be based on an index based on the average of the two measures. ***Champion*** ***endline survey***.

Mechanism 1: Perceptions of Outgroup. The intervention might change the champions’ perceptions of outgroup individuals. We therefore ask a question that measures *Social Distance*:

“How comfortable are you having neighbors who have different beliefs or values?”

1- Not at all comfortable; 2- Not too comfortable; 3- Somewhat comfortable; 4- Extremely comfortable; -99- Don’t know

Champion ***endline survey***.

Mechanism 2: Internal Political Efficacy. The intervention might change the champions’ perception of their internal political efficacy, that is, their ability to understand, participate, and shape politics. We ask:

“I can convince people to register and turn out to vote.”

“I consider myself to be well qualified to participate in the electoral process.”

4-Strongly agree; 3-Somewhat agree; 2-Neither agree nor disagree; 1-Somewhat disagree;
0-Strongly disagree; -99-DK/Refuse"

Champion endline survey.

Mechanism 3: External Political Efficacy. The intervention might change the champions' perception of external political efficacy, that is, the extent to which the state is responsive to civilian demands. We ask two questions:

"The 2023 election will be free and fair.."

"People like me have no influence at all on what the government does."

"The 2023 election is an opportunity for citizens to impact government services."

4-Strongly agree; 3-Somewhat agree; 2-Neither agree nor disagree; 1-Somewhat disagree;
0-Strongly disagree; -99-DK/Refuse"

Champion endline survey.

Mechanism 4: Perceptions of Social Value Voting. The intervention might change the champions' perceptions of how relatives, friends, and other close relationships value electoral participation. We ask:

"How many of your friends and family will vote in 2023?"

How many of your friends and family are already registered to vote in 2023?"

5-All of them; 4-Most of them; 3-About half of them; 2-A few of them; 1-None of them;
-99-Don't know/Refuse

How much do you think your close friends and family members want you to vote in 2023?"

5- My friends and family really want me to vote; 4-My friends and family kind of want me to vote; 3- My friends and family don't care if I vote; 2-My friends and family kind of don't want me to vote; 1-My friends and family really don't want me to vote; -99. Don't know/Refuse

Champion endline survey.

Mechanism 5: Civic Duty. The intervention might change the champions' perception of the value of electoral participation. We ask:

"Zimbabwean citizens have a duty to vote in the 2023 election."

4-Strongly agree; 3-Somewhat agree; 2-Neither agree nor disagree; 1-Somewhat disagree;
0-Strongly disagree; -99-DK/Refuse"

Champion endline survey.

Mechanism 6: Unintended Consequences. The intervention might change the champions' perceptions of the level of democracy in Zimbabwe. We ask:

"In the last three months, have you faced any problems because of your political beliefs or actions?"

In the last three months, has a candidate or someone from a political party offered you something, like food, a gift, or money, in return for your vote?"

0- No, 1 - Yes, 9- Don't know

"How much do you fear becoming a victim of political violence around the 2023 election?"

5- Not at all; 4- A little bit; 3-Somewhat; 2-A lot; 9-Don't know

Demographics 1: Network Centrality. We will ask about the network centrality of each champion. To measure network centrality, we ask the following question:

"Now I am going to read out a list of groups that people join or attend. For each one, could you tell me whether you are an official leader, an active member, an inactive member, or not a member."

A religious group that meets outside of regular worship services?

An agriculture or farming group?

A residents' association?

A women's group?

A savings and lending association?

A business or craft association or a union?

Some other kind of association or group?

1-Official leader; 2-Active member; 3-Inactive member; 4-Not a member; -99-DK/Refuse

[IF YES] What other association or group are you part of?"

*Champion baseline survey.*²

Demographics 2: Partisanship. We will measure the partisan preferences of the champions. We ask the following two questions:

"1. Do you approve or disapprove of the way that your MEMBER OF PARLIAMENT has performed their jobs over the past 12 months, or haven't you heard enough about them to say?"

² If we do not have baseline data for a champion, we will ask these baseline questions at endline. We will test whether the treatment has any measurable effect on the endline measures of these baseline characteristics both overall and in all demographic subgroups. If there is no detectable effect, we will use the endline measures as moderators in our analyses.

1-Strongly approve; 2-Approve; 3-Neither approve nor disapprove; 4-Disapprove; 5-Strongly disapprove; -99-DK/Refuse”

“2. Do you approve or disapprove of the way that your ELECTED LOCAL GOVERNMENT COUNCILOR has performed their jobs over the past 12 months, or haven't you heard enough about them to say?

1-Strongly approve; 2-Approve; 3-Neither approve nor disapprove; 4-Disapprove; 5-Strongly disapprove; -99-DK/Refuse"

3. Do you know who your MEMBER OF PARLIAMENT is?

4. Do you know who your ELECTED LOCAL GOVERNMENT COUNCILOR is?

1-Yes; 2-No; -99-Not sure

We will merge these questions with information on the constituency and ward of the respondent and their representatives' party affiliations to infer their partisanship. If someone approves of a ZANU-PF councilor or MP, we will code them as pro-ZANU. If they approve of a non-ZANU-PF councilor or MP, we will code them as pro-opposition. If they don't know or have mixed approval (one pro-ZANU approval and one pro-opposition approval) we will code them as independent.

Champion baseline survey.

Project Output 1: Knowledge of Voter Registration. We will measure the champions' knowledge of the voter registration process. We ask:

"Now I'd like to ask you some questions about how to register to vote.

Do you need to pay a fee to register to vote?"

1-Yes; 2-No

Do you need proof of residence to register to vote?

1-Yes; 2-No

Can you register to vote with a driver's license?

1-Yes; 2-No

Can you tell me the shortcode to check whether you are registered to vote?"

These knowledge questions will be combined into a numeric index of the number of correct answers.

Champion baseline and endline survey.

Project Output 2: Voter Registration Attempts. We will measure the attempts of champions to mobilize potential voters. We ask the following:

"In the past three months, have you tried to help anyone get registered to vote, even if you were not successful?"

1-Yes; 0-No

[IF YES] How many people have you tried to get registered to vote in the past three months?

[numeric]

[IF YES] Did you have all the information that you needed during your conversations about voter registration?

[IF YES] How effective do you think you were in convincing people to get registered to vote?

0-Not at all effective; 1-A little bit effective; 2-Somewhat effective; 3-Very effective; -99-Don't know"

[IF NO] Why didn't you try to help anyone get registered to vote?

1-I didn't have time

2-I didn't feel comfortable contacting them

3-They were already registered

4-I knew I couldn't convince them

The way that we ask these questions will depend on the survey mode. For champions surveyed in automated WhatsApp surveys, we will ask them the questions as written above. For champions surveyed by enumerators over the phone, we will ask the same questions about each peer that they were assigned to try to get registered to vote.

Champion endline survey.

Answer Strategy

We will estimate the ITT of assignment to participate in the champions program compared to control using covariate-adjusted difference-in-means. We will control for the following covariates: CSO, champion gender, champion age category, and champion constituency.

We will analyze this data as a single RCT (as opposed to as a meta-analysis of 11 individual RCTs).

To take into account the differences in the probability of assignment to treatment we will weight observations using inverse propensity weights.

Second, we will estimate the conditional IIT of assignment to any treatment across subgroups in order to better understand how the program works. We will estimate these conditional IITs using covariate-adjusted difference-in-means using the interaction of treatment assignment and the baseline characteristics of interest. Specifically, we will estimate whether the treatment varies for champions who are assigned to mobilize more peers who share their same partisanship group and demographic characteristics. We will also estimate whether the treatment is more or less effective in places where electoral participation is higher cost, measured by the historical incidence of election-related violence in the ACLED data and distance to the nearest voter registration center and national ID center. These variables are described in more depth in the main study paper (Dendere & Young 2022).

Ethical Considerations

Two of the researchers (Dendere and Young) are unpaid consultants working under a Memorandum of Understanding with the National Democratic Institute's DC office of evaluation and learning. They are participating in this evaluation as academics and are free to use the data from the study without conditions. The National Democratic Institute and their CSO partners are responsible for the champions intervention. This program is being carried out under a multiyear grant from USAID Zimbabwe to promote democracy and governance in Zimbabwe.

The researchers have obtained IRB approval for their participation in the research. The UC Davis IRB has determined that the researchers are only responsible for the data collection process and that the research is exempt. The risk posed by a loss of confidentiality during measurement is minimal as we will not be asking sensitive questions and will de-identify the data. While some forms of political participation such as protest or campaigning on behalf of the main opposition party are often sensitive in Zimbabwe, registering to vote or participating in surveys about politics is generally not. NDI and its data collection partner PPRIZ will set up systems to keep survey responses separate from identifying information to minimize the risk of loss of confidentiality.

Although we are not technically responsible for the champions intervention under IRB guidelines, we believe that programs being evaluated by academics should still meet a minimal beneficence threshold. One reason for this is that our collaboration with NDI could be interpreted as an implicit endorsement of the program. Our collaboration will also hopefully enable its architects to operate more effectively. We see this voter registration program as meeting a reasonable standard of beneficence. The goals of the donor USAID, NDI, and the CSOs are broadly to increase the political participation of groups like women and youth that are under-represented in the Zimbabwean electorate. The CSOs are all nominally non-partisan groups where political party affiliation is not a de jure or de facto requirement for membership. Their theory of change is broadly that more and more equal participation could bring about more responsive policy and perhaps a liberalizing electoral outcome in this type of regime and make policy more responsive, particularly at a local level. Given this, we do not expect that participating in the program is likely to put the champions or peers at increased risk of harm or have negative systemic effects.

Bibliography

Kalla, Joshua L., and David E. Broockman. 2022. "Voter Outreach Campaigns Can Reduce Affective Polarization among Implementing Political Activists: Evidence from Inside Three Campaigns." *American Political Science Review*, March, 1–7.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003055422000132>.

Niemi, Richard G., Stephen C. Craig, and Franco Mattei. 1991. "Measuring Internal Political Efficacy in the 1988 National Election Study." *American Political Science Review* 85 (4): 1407–13. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1963953>.

Paolini, Stefania, Jake Harwood, and Mark Rubin. 2010. "Negative Intergroup Contact Makes Group Memberships Salient: Explaining Why Intergroup Conflict Endures." *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin* 36 (12): 1723–38. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167210388667>.

Pettigrew, Thomas F. 1998. "Intergroup Contact Theory." *Annual Review of Psychology* 49 (1): 65–85. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.49.1.65>.

Wood, Elisabeth. 2003. *Insurgent Collective Action and Civil War in El Salvador*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.